

CDE4Peace

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CONCEPT DEVELOPMENT AND EXPERIMENTATION FOR EU CONFLICT PREVENTION AND PEACE-BUILDING (CDE4PEACE)

Interviews

March – November 2021

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Executive Summary

This document presents the transcripts of 25 qualitative interviews conducted under the CDE4Peace project in the period March – November 2021. In line with the project’s Data Management Plan the qualitative interviews are fully anonymised and deposited on the Zenodo platform for open access.

Interview no.1 with an official from the European Union Military Staff (EUMS)

Date: 09/03/2021

1. Describe briefly the role of Concept development and experimentation (CD&E) within the EUMS and EEAS?

CD&E does exist within the EUMS, although the conceptual development has to take place without any support of experimentation (due to a huge lack of the needed resources). And, the conceptual development is not comparable to the efforts within NATO.

2. What legal or policy documents regulate CD&E within the EEAS? Are there any classified documents in this sphere?

1. Framework for EU Military Conceptual Development (LIMITÉ, ST 6863/17, dated 2 March 2017)
2. European Union Military Experimentation Concept (ST 17293/12, dated 5 December 2012)
3. (new one each year) EU Military Conceptual Development Implementation Programme 2020-2021 (CDIP 20-21) (LIMITÉ, ST 7990/20, dated 13 May 2020)

3. Have CD&E methods (e.g., operational analysis) been used in the planning or lessons learned phase of concrete CSDP missions and operations so far?

Not that I am aware of.

The EUMS does not have any of those resources like OA or M&S, it is dependent on Member States or (if applicable) on „good will“ by NATO .

4. Have CD&E methods (e.g., modelling and simulation, wargaming) been employed in exercises organized by the EUMS/EEAS so far? Do you know any exercise-based experiments at the EU level?

Due to the severe lack of resources and not having any funds to use such methods, the EUMS always tries to cooperate with e.g. the Joint Research Center or the EUISS to achieve at least something. The whole landscape of exercises is also very different from NATO exercises.

5. What technological solutions and software tools for CD&E purposes do you use in your work within the EUMS / EEAS? Judging from your experience, are there available CD&E tools on the European market? Please, specify your level of satisfaction with the available solutions.

The military within the EU is just a very tiny entity. It is per se not comparable with NATO at all. Just compare the NATO Command Structure of at least 6.500 men and women, having ACT and ACO and so on, with the EUMS and the MPCC (together less than 300).

6. Could you describe briefly technological solutions or software tools for CD&E purposes which would be helpful for your work.

Drafting a Concept is undertaken by a single person, one Action Officer. He or she brings up the draft for the Member States. Within the European Union Military Committee (EUMC) Working Group they are usually being finalised and agreed on EUMC level, meaning agreed by the Member States.

There is no project behind a conceptual development like it is in ACT, where different entities are being used or funded in order to bring up the concept.

7. Do you consider the NATO methodology for Concept development and experimentation (CD&E) to be relevant for the EU's Common Security and Defence Policy as a whole? In your view what would be the effect of more active application of CD&E methods on the CSDP / EU conflict prevention and peace-building?

As many „ACT-minded“ officers have seen NATO, national CD&E or Transformation in one of their former appointments, the „spirit“ of CD&E (or of transformation in general) is within the people.

But, the EEAS nor the EUMS, the Council or the EUMC are fit for purpose for more CD&E. We don't even do large-scale exercises ... If you look into the Member States itself, you will see that only some of them do have their own national entities for CD&E. Many of them do completely rely on NATO.

The EU in general may use more CD&E within the Commission, as there is the quantity.

8. Do you consider CD&E to be applicable to EU defence planning and capability development? Could the CD&E methodology be applied in concrete EU capability development projects under the PESCO framework?

Within defence planning and capability development the EUMS already tries to make use of more „CD&E“ in cooperation with the Commission (JRC) and the NATO STO organisation. Doing more without staff is just not possible.

PESCO is Member States driven, the story repeats, it is on the participating Member States to do it.

9. From your perspective what would be the added value of the CD&E methodology in CSDP operation (mission) planning and lessons learned? For example, could CD&E be helpful in defining mission mandates?

If it eases the job to be done by the respective Action Officer, yes, than it adds value. But, look into the details how such a mandate is being processed within the EU ... I would say that in most cases there is time pressure and Member States consensus.

Usually there is no room for „additional CD&E burden“, as it may be seen by the Action Officer.

10. Do you find CD&E relevant for strategic concepts in the area of CSDP, such as resilience, strategic autonomy, etc.?

Relevant, yes. Feasible, no.

In theory it is brilliant, but in practical terms the management/organising task to make use of it is just overwhelming.

11. How could gender aspects be taken into account in the application of CD&E methods within the EUMS / EEAS?

I have no answer to that question.

12. Have you made use of the results from EU research and innovation projects in your work? Please specify the name of the project/s and how they were helpful.

I did not.

In general: Systematically this is not taking place. If it happens, then occasionally, mostly out of coincidence.

13. Could you propose measures for enhancing cooperation between research and policy on CD&E at the EU level?

I have no answer to that question.

14. How would you assess cooperation with the NATO CD&E bodies? In your view what are the prospects of EU-NATO collaboration on CD&E?

I would describe it as being aware of each other.

As the EUMS does not have anything really comparable with the NATO CD&E it is hard to get any beneficial collaboration established.

The EUMS is the single military expertise within the EU, keeping contact from the Office of the Secretary General, the International Staff, the International Military Staff, HQ SACT, SHAPE and even more below.

EU and NATO are just not comparable, don't have the same "setting". Therefore, bringing NATO CD&E into the EU is not an easy fix.

Interview no.2 with a representative of the European Centre of Excellence for Civilian Crisis Management

Date: 23/03/2021

1. Describe briefly in what ways does the European Centre of Excellence (CoE) practically help for enhancing civilian capacities in EU crisis management? How is the impact from CoE activities measured?

The CoE supports its members, which currently are 19 EU Member States, and its preferred partner, the EEAS (Nato IS is a preferred partner, too), in achieving their commitments and the overall goals of the civilian CSDP Compact. The CoE does so by offering advice, exchange of knowledge / good practices and tailored solutions to its members, helping them to operationalize their commitments and translate them into concrete steps.

As the CoE is a service provider for its members and preferred partners, the impact of its activities is measured in terms of the number of specific requests with which the Centre is approached. Such requests can lead to the CoE organising workshops, setting up a mentoring programme or advising on specific administrative reform processes. The impact of these activities is in turn measured through continuous and close interaction with members and preferred partners. This way the CoE receives feedback on its activities and information on their impact in terms of follow-up actions and processes at the EU or national level.

2. What part of the overall CoE activities do the analysis and research on EU crisis management amount to? What research methodologies are employed in the analytical work of the CoE?

The CoE is neither a think tank nor a research organisation. Its role is that of a service provider for its members and preferred partners (cf. question 1). Accordingly, the CoE responds to specific needs and requests rather than engaging independently in analysis and research. At the same time, when tailoring solutions to specific needs and requests from its members or the EEAS, the CoE takes account of the latest analysis and research on EU civilian crisis management and augments these findings. To give a practical example, this could mean that policy advice and recommendations by other actors is taken up by the CoE and translated to a specific national context in terms of concrete actions the respective CoE member could take. Employed methodologies range from desk research through interviews and surveys to quantitative analysis e.g. of HR statistics.

3. What technological solutions and software tools do you use in your work for enhancing EU civilian crisis management? Please, specify your level of satisfaction with the available solutions.

The CoE's Knowledge Hub is at the core of the Centre's efforts to enhance EU civilian crisis management. For software solutions and tools used, please refer to question 4. As the Knowledge Hub will only be launched in April, it is at this stage too early to assess either our own or our members' satisfaction with the respective software solutions and tools.

4. Describe briefly the CoE's Knowledge Hub. What tools are used for its development?

The CoE's Knowledge Hub will go live with a relaunch of the CoE's website in April 2021. Once launched, its scope and functionalities will be expanded continuously. In a first step the Knowledge Hub will become available as a pool of resources (i.e. documents, media files, links to relevant other websites or platforms etc.) on EU civilian crisis management topically structured along the lines of the CoE's workstrands. Available resources will be easily accessible and navigable through a powerful search function. In further steps, the Hub will be expanded to 1) include an upload centre through which users can feed further resources into the Knowledge Hub; 2) offer forums in which users will be able to comment on available resources and engage in topical discussions; 3) include a chat bot and other web applications allowing users to specifically tap data, information and knowledge that could inform e.g. national reform efforts aimed at strengthening civilian CSDP.

As the Knowledge Hub is operated on the CoE's website, it is developed based on the content management system "Typo3". Other applications and add-ons to realise the aforementioned tools and functionalities are used as fit.

5. Are tools for modelling and simulation (M&S), wargaming or gaming for peace used in the work of the CoE? If yes, please specify the product/s.

Neither of these tools are currently used in the work of the CoE.

6. Are you acquainted with the NATO methodology and process for Concept development and experimentation (CD&E)? If yes, do you consider this methodology relevant for EU civilian crisis management?

We are not acquainted with this methodology in depth and are currently not using it in our work.

7. What are the relations of the CoE with the European academia and the research industry? Have you made use of the results from EU research and innovation projects in the area of EU crisis management?

The CoE is in contact with some think tanks and its team regularly reads up on current papers and publications in this realm. It also contributes to publications and events organized either by the CoE itself or think tanks. As part of our outreach strategy, connections with further academic institutions, foundations and research institutes will be deepened in the coming months. Our current work and development of future activities is therefore informed by the results of researchers and innovative projects.

8. What are the main priorities of the CoE in terms of gender mainstreaming in EU civilian crisis management?

Besides the overall considerations of gender mainstreaming in all aspects of civilian crisis management, which is one of the work priorities of the Centre, the CoE's main priority for its current workplan lies in increasing women's representation at all levels of civilian CSDP missions, especially in regards to secondment in general, but also leadership roles.

9. Is military crisis management fully excluded from the CoE's remit? Given that 'civilian' and 'defence' have opposite meanings, how does the designation 'civilian' align with the Common Security and Defence Policy under the Civilian CSDP Compact?

The focus and mandate of the CoE lies by its nature clearly in strengthening the civilian side of the EU's crisis management. However, also with a view to the EU's integrated approach to CSDP, the CoE does consider identifying synergies an important aspect of its work, especially in the field, where both military and civilian missions are deployed in the same theatre. Cooperation with NATO as preferred partner is sought specifically in the realm of civil-military cooperation. More tangibly and against the backdrop of the ongoing EU-NATO strategic partnership, cooperation could be useful in already identified areas of cooperation such as hybrid threats, cyber security, capacity building.

With a view to the Civilian CSDP Compact, civilian means certainly belong more within the realm of the Security aspect of CSDP, while interlinkages of its effects may also be of relevance for Defense Policy considerations. Increasing strategic exchange, cooperation and coordination between both Security and Defense actors is therefore an important part of the CoE's work. This is even more relevant with a view to the internal-external security nexus.

Synergies between CPCC and MPCC should be sought. This will be advocated for by the CoE.

Civilian CSDP ought to figure prominently in the emerging Strategic Compass, a goal which the CoE is pursuing actively through participation in a number of fora.

10. What is the CoEs' experience in conducting (or taking part in) training and exercises for peace-building missions?

The CoE does not conduct training for peace-building missions, nor has it taken part in them. Nevertheless, the CoE takes a comprehensive view of the overall EU training infrastructure for civilian crisis management and works with its partners to bring about concrete change on a systemic level in support of the implementation of the EU Policy on Training for CSDP.

11. Have you made use of tools for concept development and experimentation (CD&E) in training and exercises? If yes, please specify the product.

We have not, since we are not conducting trainings (cf. question 9) at the moment.

12. Given that the CoE is the first of its kind in the EU, what is your level of ambition for the next 3-4 years? Would it be realistic for the CoE to become a major player on the fragmented EU crisis management scene?

The CoE is committed to becoming a “one-stop-shop” in the field of European civilian crisis management, providing expertise, and supporting our members concretely in their capacities to act and reach their goals within the implementation of the Civilian CSDP Compact by 2023, and beyond. As an association positioned in between member states, Brussels institutions and the missions, the CoE can play a strong role in facilitating exchange and supporting the implementation of goals and lessons learnt on the different levels to contribute to a more capable, more effective, flexible and responsive as well as a more joined-up civilian CSDP. In that sense, the CoE supports the major players in the EU crisis management scene in aligning and enhancing their efforts.

Interview no. 3 with a representative of the Bulgarian Modelling and Simulation Association – BULSIM

Date: 05/04/2021

1. What are the main challenges for promoting M&S knowledge and the use of simulation methods in your country?

There are no main challenges for promoting M&S knowledge in Bulgaria. The main challenge for the use of simulation methods, can be said, is the natural requirement of those methods and tools to have higher than medium skills and competences to understand the algorithms behind and applied them in a proper way to obtain maximum results. The lack of well-educated resources can be considered also.

2. Is your organization developing M&S products? If yes, please describe your main M&S product.

BULSIM is a non-profit organization for public benefit, dedicated to spreading and recognition of the modeling and simulation in Bulgaria and doesn't develop its M&S products.

BULSIM assists people and organizations from research, government, industrial and non-government sectors by means of analysis, consultations, education and training, for which the competences and capabilities of its members, as well M&S approach and tools, will contribute for their growth and positioning in the society and business.

However, the members of BULSIM are working for companies or universities where M&S products are developed or widely used.

3. Which are the major national and international end-users of M&S products? What is the role of different organizations (civilian, military, educational, research) for shaping the M&S industry?

The major end-users of M&S products in Bulgaria are the Ministry of Defence (mainly for training purposes), Crises Management and Disaster Response Center of Excellence, Ministry of Interior, Air Traffic Authority, the Universities and the Training Centers. Also the financial and insurance companies. Internationally the end-users are similar including NATO, ESA and NASA.

M&S development is a good example for synergy between industry, academia and government. The main role for shaping the M&S industry have all of them.

4. Can we speak of a well-developed European market of M&S products? Which are the major players on this market?

Unfortunately no. Currently the M&S market is in its growing stage, however not so far from its maturity. The major players are the companies developing M&S products for training, decision support, research and analyses.

5. Could you specify the most technologically mature M&S products in your country? Which of them could be considered competitive on the European market?

In Bulgaria the companies mostly assemble simulators and/or develop models and content for simulations. Also apply various international tools during CAXes. However there is a Bulgarian competitive approach/solution for CAX management and also simulators based on world leading game engines as VBS, Unity and Unreal Engine.

6. Do you know of any M&S tools that are relevant for EU conflict prevention and peace-building or the EU's Common Security and Defence Policy (CSDP)?

M&S tools relevant for EU conflict prevention and peace-building or the EU's Common Security and Defence Policy (CSDP) are SWORD/SYNERGY of the French company MASA Group, EXONAUT of the Swedish company 4CStrategies, JTLS of the American corporation Rolands&Associates and others that can model and simulate the processes.

7. Has your organization been involved in Concept development and experimentation (CD&E)? Have you made use of M&S tools for CD&E purposes (e.g., in exercises)?

Yes. BULSIM has participated in several computer assisted exercises since its establishment. BULSIM was the first ever organization in Bulgaria that planned, conducted and analyzed CAX for cybersecurity for the government organizations in which various concepts were developed and through experiments adapted, validated and verified, or rejected as unfeasible. During the exercises were used various M&S tools to create the environment, plan and run scenarios and lessons learnt analyses.

8. In your view how could M&S support Concept development and experimentation? Do you consider M&S methods and tools to be scientifically credible?

Definitely yes. M&S could support the Concept Development process highly effectively by modeling and evaluating various alternatives for a short time. And then through the experimentation process to access the applicability of each of those alternatives. M&S has experience on expertise on conceptual modelling and supporting cross-disciplinary problem solving.

As M&S is entirely based on scientific research and development so its credibility is not questionable. However it all depends on the accuracy of the models developed and used for simulation. Also the simulation high fidelity is of great importance.

9. In your view how could gender aspects be integrated in M&S activities?

Gender aspects as equality and mainstreaming are integrated naturally in M&S activities. The competences and skills are not dependent on a specific gender rather than the individual itself.

10. From your experience which M&S methods and tools used in computer-assisted exercises (CAX) are best suited to represent the complexities of reality?

There are many M&S methods and tools on the market which are applied depending on the specific aims and target audience of CAXes. No general or short answer of this question.

Interview no.4 with officials from the European External Action Service (EEAS)

Date: 08/04/2021

1. Describe briefly your day-to-day activities on coordinating PESCO. Which is the most challenging part of working under the PESCO framework?

PESCO is a MS driven initiative and a framework for cooperation among those MS whose military capabilities fulfil higher criteria and which have made commitments to one another with a view to the most demanding missions and contributing to the fulfilment of the Union LOA. Under the responsibility of the High Representative, also in his capacity as the Head of the EDA, the necessary secretariat functions for PESCO (PeSec) are provided jointly by the EEAS, including the EUMS, and the EDA, as described in Art 7(2) of the Council Decision (CFSP) 2017/2315.

As such, the day-to-day PESCO-related activities are along the tasks described in the respective article. Perhaps a challenging aspect of PESCO is to ensure coordination and consultation among the PeSec members, as this is not a standing structure, while also acting as a honest broker both to the MS and other EU institutions (e.g. Commission) who have an interest in PESCO.

2. Could you single out 2-3 PESCO projects that have already delivered concrete and promising results? What is the mechanism for review of ongoing and completed PESCO projects?

PESCO is a framework for cooperation aiming inter alia at supporting capability development which, by default, is a medium to long term endeavour. Only three years after the adoption of the first wave of PESCO projects, it is too early to highlight full operational capability for them. However, as pointed out in the Council Conclusions on the PESCO Strategic Review 2020 – PSR 2020 (doc no 13188/20), there is a whole list of projects (26) planned to deliver concrete results / full operational capability before the end of the PESCO phase 2021-2025. At the same time, some PESCO projects managed to achieve concrete results (e.g. EUFOR CROC has managed to prepare the first Force Element List – FEL for the Support to HA and DR scenario and MS have already submitted their contributions to the respective database) and some others are approaching their initial operational capability in the coming years, cognizant that the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic has had an impact on their implementation. Moreover, 8 out of the 46 PESCO projects launched so far are linked to 9 projects awarded under the 2019 EDIDP calls, while two more PESCO projects are linked to 2 projects to be awarded under direct award procedure in the light of the agreed EDIDP 2019-2020 Work Programme.

3. What technological solutions and software tools do you use in your work for managing PESCO projects?

The PESCO projects are managed by the participating MS, with one or more of them designated project coordinator(s). In order to facilitate the work of the MS, PeSec prepared, launched and has managed a so-called electronic PESCO Common Work Space (CWS), which is an electronic platform for which MS designated their POCs (including national POCs coordinator). The CWS is used both as

a repository for PESCO as well as to facilitate interactions among MS as well as between them and PeSec.

PESCO project proposals are assessed based on a set of assessment criteria, including both capability perspective and operational perspective, while MS are encouraged to use project management tools and techniques in order to implement their projects. Annually, based on MS inputs, all PESCO projects progress is reported, with the PSR 2020 recommending the development of progress and risk indicators, as well as criteria for success, with a view to provide for more transparency in their progress. Given its supporting role, the PeSec has taken forward those recommendations and the related indicators are being used in assessing and reporting PESCO projects progress. Moreover, a dedicated PESCO Project Management course is to be organised together with ESDC and to be dispensed to MS experts proposing and /or implementing PESCO projects (a pilot course is scheduled for June 2021, with regular bi-annual iterations foreseen afterwards, as of fall 2021).

4. How are technological concepts under PESCO projects tested and validated? Are there any special requirements to the project coordinators to include experimentation in the projects?

In line with the PESCO commitments, the PESCO projects fall under two main categories: operational (including training) and capability development, so rather addressing stages beyond technological concepts (in particular for capability development related projects).

Given the two-layered governance of PESCO (i.e. at the level of Council, and in the framework of projects implemented by groups of those MS which agreed among themselves to undertake such projects), it is up to project members to decide upon the objectives and scope of the PESCO projects.

5. Is there a coordination mechanism between the EU defence R&D initiatives (PESCO, EDF) and EU civilian R&D programmes (Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe)?

The main EU defence related initiatives (PESCO, CARD, EDF) contributing to the fulfilment of the EU LOA in security and defence were established as consistent and mutually reinforcing, while being distinct and having different legal bases. Their coherence is ensured by the High Representative/Vice-President of the Commission, also in his capacity as the Head of the EDA, who has prepared, since 2019, the so-called Report on interactions, links and coherence among the respective initiatives. At the same time, the EU Capability Development Priorities, which also take into account the CSDP military shortfalls, provide a key reference for MS and EU capability development, including by informing all respective EU defence initiatives. Moreover, the PESCO projects and the new CARD collaborative opportunities, inform the preparation of EDF annual WPs. Last but not least, the Draft EDF Regulation (Art 28(a)) foresees that the EDA is invited as an observer and the EEAS to assist in the proceedings of the EDF Programme Committee (and currently in the informal expert group on EDF), thus ensuring coherence and consistency among PESCO, CARD and EDF, as well as with the EU CDPs.

When it comes to the EU civilian R&D programmes, it is worth noting the possibility (IAW Art 7(1) of the Council Decision (CFSP) 2018/909 on governance rules for PESCO projects) for Commission's involvement, as appropriate, in the proceedings of individual PESCO projects.

And perhaps not less important, the evaluation of the EDIDP (and soon EDF) proposals is conducted in several stages and based on a set of award and selection criteria, also with the involvement of independent experts as well as various Commission departments and agencies representatives, thus ensuring coordination with EU civilian R&D programmes (including H2020 and soon HE).

6. What is the role of your unit in managing the European Defence Fund and the EDIDP? Do you take part in defining the calls under the EDF?

In accordance with the EDIDP Regulation and Draft EDF Regulations, the Commission is to adopt the work programmes and it is to be assisted by a committee made up of MS representatives.

The respective Regulations also foresee that the EDA is invited as an observer and the EEAS to assist in the proceedings of their respective Programme Committee (and currently in the informal expert group on EDF), thus ensuring coherence and consistency among PESCO, CARD and EDF, as well as with the EU CDPs.

Through the EEAS (including the EUMS) presence, coherence is ensured as well with the so-called High Impact Capability Goals (HICG) identified under the Headline Goal and representing the most efficient way of pursuing the fulfilment of the EU CSDP Military LOA.

7. Are you acquainted with the NATO methodology and process for Concept development and experimentation (CD&E)? If yes, do you consider this methodology relevant for PESCO and EDF?

NATO's CDE methodology is rather used by the EUMS colleagues, with a dedicated Concepts Unit / Division / Branch dealing with these aspects, based on a so-called Concept Development Implementation Programme, which is covering a two-year horizon.

8. How does your unit take into account gender aspects in the management of projects under PESCO and the EDF?

According to our information, these aspects are not criteria specifically put forward in the management of PESCO projects by the projects' coordinators.

9. How would you assess cooperation with NATO on defence R&D? In your view what are the prospects of EU-NATO collaboration on defence R&D in the future?

For R&D aspects, the interface with NATO is ensured by the EDA. The annual progress reports on the implementation of the 2016 and 2018 EU-NATO Joint Declarations present a detailed state of play in this respect. Recent interactions between the EU and NATO, as well as in the light of the

NATO 2030 reflection and the work in the context of the so-called EU Strategic Compass point into the direction of greater interactions between the two organisations in R&D, in particular as regards EDTs.

10. Could you propose measures for enhancing cooperation between research and policy in the area of the EU's Common Security and Defence Policy, conflict prevention and peace-building?

Technological development will continue to be an important driver for capability development. In fact, in identifying EU CDPs, beyond CSDP military capability shortfalls and lessons learned from missions and operations, as well as MS defence plans, the long-term technological trends are also used in order to derive their impact on capability development.

Moreover, in the context of the capabilities basket of the so-called EU Strategic Compass, the intent is to also look into ways to promote technological sovereignty and innovation, including by reflecting on the impact of EDTs for future CSDP missions and operations, both to increase operational effectiveness and efficiency and to mitigate their potential malicious use by adversaries. Last but not least, CSDP / security & defence related policies will have to better take into account the EDTs with a view to increase the EU's resilience, enhance links between climate and defence, ensure further interactions with and contribute to an innovative and competitive EDTIB...

As far as conflict prevention and peace- building are concerned, these are areas of competence under another EEAS directorate, Integrated Approach for Security and Peace (ISP), which you may consider to contact as well.

Interview no.5 with a European Union Military Staff (EUMS) official-2

Date: 08/04/2021

1. Some experts claim that the capability shortfalls identified by NATO defence planning process (NDPP) and the EU's Capability Development Plan (CDP) are nearly identical. In this context how would you address the critique of existing duplication between NATO and EU defence planning?

Do not fully agree with these claims. The capability priorities are different. In the EU defence planning process (the Headline Goal Process – HLGP), most of the steps follow those in NDPP- step 1, step 2, step 5. Step 4 can be compared to the EU CDP as it pertains the capability development endeavour. The exception is step 3 (apportion requirements and set targets) which is missing in EU defence planning.

With this in mind, the capability shortfalls identified in the NDPP are to be compared with the High Impact Capability Goals (HICGs) stemming from the EU Progress Catalogue, and not the CDP outcomes.

Common EU and NATO shortfalls can be identified comparing the HICGs with the NATO Main Shortfall Areas (or Defence planning Priorities).

2. Are NATO and EU defence planning actually comparable? More specifically, are the five steps in the NDPP replicated in the EU in some ways?

Since 2018 EU defence planning (HLGP) has been aligned with NATO. Within the EU, CDP is taken by EDA, while capability planning is done by the EUMS, EUMC and the Council. We (EUMS) use the same taxonomy, the same language as NATO, while EDA uses a different taxonomy.

3. In NATO Concept development and experimentation (CD&E) provides input to step 2 - determine requirements, step 3 - apportion requirements and set targets, and step 4 -facilitate implementation in the NDPP. In which steps of the EU defence planning process could CD&E potentially provide input?

In my view CD&E could provide input to the entire defence planning process – step 2, step 4 and why not in step 1 (political guidance). CD&E could support strategic political guidance. We need to build a common understanding, a common strategic culture. Doctrines are concepts and they need to be experimented. We need common narratives.

4. Have CD&E methods (e.g., modelling and simulation, wargaming, alternative analysis) been employed in EU defence planning so far?

To very limited extent. We have worked on scenarios and exercises, but we lack resources (compared with NATO).

This year a contract will be signed between the EEAS and NATO Communications and Information (NCI) Agency for software tools and databases. One of the software tools used by NCI is JDARTS (Joint Defence Planning Analytical Requirements).

5. Have you made use of the results from EU research and innovation projects in your work on EU defence planning? Please specify the name of the project/s and how they were helpful.

Not really, but we have established cooperation with the JRC on strategic foresight and strategic autonomy.

6. Have you made use of Member States' CD&E capabilities / projects in your work on EU defence planning so far?

Not really.

7. Do you consider CD&E to be applicable to EU defence (and civilian) planning and, more specifically to the CPD, CARD and the Headline Goal Process (HLGP)?

Yes, absolutely. CD&E could help both the EUMS and EDA in their work on defence planning.

8. Could the CD&E methodology be applied in concrete EU capability development projects under the PESCO framework? More specifically, in which of the six focus areas of capability development identified in the CARD report 2020 would technology testing (as a relevant CD&E method) give most added value?

PESCO is based on two pillars: 1) capability development (projects) and 2) common binding commitments. CD&E is more relevant to capability development. A good idea would be a PESCO project on CD&E.

Within the CARD endeavour the 6 focus areas have been identified by the EDA, in addition, the EUMS has portrayed several operational collaborative opportunities (e.g., Aircraft carrier, Ballistic missile defence, etc.) which are not addressed by dedicated capability development initiatives (including PESCO) and they need a cooperative approach due to their magnitude.

CD&E could stand at the basis of PESCO projects aimed at linking capabilities together, enhancing deployability, interoperability and readiness of EU forces.

9. In your view could CD&E be applied in a meaningful way in the EU's strategic foresight analysis, (e.g. under the Strategic Compass)?

Yes, there are big links. Without reinventing the wheel, CD&E could be used in the EU's strategic foresight analysis as it is done in NATO.

10. In your view what would be the most appropriate institutionalization of a CD&E Cell at the EU level: 1) in the EEAS/EUMS; 2) in the European Commission; 3) in an EU research body such as the JRC, the EUISS or a dedicated European Centre of Excellence?

If it would be a CD&E Cell dealing with military issues it should be under the EUMS, an independent and more autonomous unit than the existing CD&E branch.

A Cell for civilian CD&E could be established in the Commission. Another option would be one single civil-military CD&E unit (in line with the integrated approach).

Centres of excellence tend to live their own lives closer to the academic world than to the real policy making mechanisms.

Interview no.6 with a representative of the Swedish Defence University

Date: 26/04/2021

1. Judging from your experience, in which research areas Concept development and experimentation (CD&E) is most applicable and practically relevant?

CD&E is applicable everywhere, in all research areas. The question is the most important thing and not the specific area. Usually, you start with an existing technology and you don't know from the start if this iterative process will lead to practically relevant results.

2. You make the case for explicitly including analysis, meaning operational analysis in CD&E. Given that operational analysis requires very precise data for mathematical modelling – which is very often missing in practice – what is your present view on the need for analytical support in the CD&E process?

Yes, operational analysis should be included in CD&E. I don't agree with the premise that analysis requires precise data in all cases. This holds true for 'hard' analysis, but not for the 'soft' methodologies. What is very important is the last stage, the Big experiment.

3. In your view what are the main differences between CD&E and traditional Research & Development (R&D)?

In Sweden there used to be two avenues – R&D – Research and Development, sometimes called Research & Technology (R&T) and studies. CD&E was something in between. The aim was to explore a solution in an iterative process. When you start with CD&E you don't know if you will find a solution. There are different termination criteria for CD&E.

4. Having in mind the difficulties in defining scientific rigour and 'the scientific method' could CD&E be considered a scientifically credible methodology?

It could be, if you conduct CD&E correctly. This does not mean that you can apply to social systems experiments in the form of natural sciences experiments. The natural science type of experiments, you cannot do it in CD&E. Of course, with regard to social systems experiments will be different as they have to involve human interaction, the human factor.

5. In your view could social science research methods, and more specifically qualitative research be part of the CD&E methodology?

Definitely, yes. The soft methods from the social sciences – despite being not so precise – have a role to play in CD&E.

6. What are the main lessons learned from implementing CD&E in the Swedish Armed Forces.

The lessons learned are very mixed. Very important is the stakeholder analysis. In Sweden there were many different people working with different components of CD&E. And if they don't work closely together, the results wouldn't be good.

In some respect Sweden was ahead of NATO in CD&E. Sweden (along with some NATO nations) participated in MNE (Multinational Experiments), in which not all NATO nations participated. CD&E in Sweden was linked with the Revolution in military affairs, the Comprehensive approach, with network-based thinking.

Another problem in Sweden is that we are a small country.

7. What is your view on the political control over the CD&E process?

It depends on what you mean by political control – the involvement of politicians or policy-makers, which are different groups. In Sweden the politicians started the CD&E process at the proposal from the Armed Forces. The idea was to build a CD&E factory where to test ideas for defence after the so-called 'strategic pause'. The politicians were on board but they got cold feet. They required reporting every 6 months. And the CD&E process requires more time and relatively broad freedom of action.

Interview no.7 with an official from the UK MOD Development, Concepts and Doctrine Centre

Date: 30/04/2021

1. Describe briefly how the future operating concepts are developed within the DCDC in practice?

ICB directs us to write them, a writing team is assembled, who should (in theory, but don't always) write a project initiation document. Then, we do research (and pay for some via the standing partnership through the RAB), conduct workshops, consult SMEs, write a Study Draft 1, circulate it, amend it, hold further workshops, circulate a SD2. After SD2, we create a final Ratification Draft which involves professional (within DCDC) editorial work, selection of pictures, imposition of standard DCDC colour themes and styles, circulated for final time in a format that looks like a final product. No major amendments envisaged at this late stage. Document finally put to ICB as the original tasker for their endorsement, foreword writer agreed upon (DG JFD, VCDS, CDS etc) writes foreword and signs it, then doc is published and printed with some level of supporting communications effort.

2. Are any strategic concepts developed within the DCDC (e.g., in the context of the Global Strategic Trends published by the UK MOD)?

Yes e.g. Global Strategic Trends, 7th ed.

3. What is your view on political control over concept development within the DCDC? How is political independence of the MOD think tank ensured?

As an institution of a liberal democratic regime I contest the presumption that DCDC concept development should be independent from political control: all aspects of UK Defence are inevitably responsive to political direction.

4. Does DCDC make use of concept testing in the work on concept development?

Noting that DCDC does not necessarily follow NATO nomenclature, DCDC employs planned force testing i.e. testing of planned forces against policy compliant scenarios.

5. Are any experimentation methods employed within the DCDC?

Yes: for example, the current DCDC Force Exploration programme employs seminar war games, literature searches, historical analyses and semi-structured interviews.

6. Does DCDC make use of the NATO methodology for Concept development and experimentation (CD&E)? Is there a point of contact for CD&E within the DCDC?

A number of DCDC personnel have undertaken the NATO CD&E cse. However, UK Defence follows processes described in the DCDC Defence Experimentation for Force Development Handbook (2020) which sometimes diverge from NATO methodology.

7. Does DCDC participate in any NATO CD&E projects under the CD&E Programme of work managed by NATO Supreme Allied Commander Transformation (SACT)? If yes, please specify the name of the project and the role of DCDC.

No.

8. How are gender aspects taken into account in the concept development process within the DCDC?

Senior DCDC military and civilian personnel are identified as Director DCDC's gender leads.

Interview no.8 with a representative of Frequentis AG

Date: 28/05/2021

The respondent does not agree to the use of anonymised quotes of the interview in publications.

Interview no.9 with a representative of Fraunhofer INT

Date: 02/06/2021

1. To what extent did the FP7 ACRIMAS project make use of Concept development and experimentation (CD&E)? Was CD&E actually applied in ACRIMAS for the development of the demonstration concept or the scenarios?

The ACRIMAS project did not apply the CD&E method, since it was as “Demonstrator Phase I” roadmapping study only, expected to propose the concept and objectives for the much larger Phase II Demonstrator Project, which became then the DRIVER project. But in ACRIMAS CD&E was selected and proposed as the method of choice for implementing the Phase II Demonstrator Project, taken from its usual defence application, since the ACRIMAS study team was convinced that CD&E should perfectly meet the challenges of a big EU Crisis Management Demonstrator project, while the concept of what “EU Crisis Management” could become was still in its infancy according to the assessment of the ACRIMAS project (with the exception of the EU Civil Protection Mechanism already established at that time).

2. Has the Institute carried out follow up projects to ACRIMAS?

The DRIVER project (phase II) is based on the findings of the ACRIMAS project and aims at two main dimensions: firstly, the development of a pan-European test-bed enabling the benchmarking of new crisis management (CM) solutions and thereby facilitating capability development through the provision of respective methodologies and infrastructure. Secondly, it aims at the actual development of a portfolio of tools that improves CM at Member State and EU level.

3. Does the Institute currently make use of the CD&E methodology in the analysis of technological trends or in the strategic planning?

The usual process in most EU innovation action projects (in which we participate) starts with the development of user requirements (after doing interviews, focus groups etc. with the end-users), the development of system requirements, an adaption or in some cases, if necessary, a technological development process of the technological solutions, pilots & demonstrations and final a final evaluation.

This waterfall process is still the preferred process of most technical partners in the projects. However, to improve the participation of the end-users in the development process, the more recent projects tend to include more and more iterative processes, e.g. mock-up or prototype tests with the end-users to be able to correct the technological development if necessary.

4. Does the Institute develop CD&E tools, tools for modelling and simulation (M&S), wargaming or peace-tech (peace-related technologies)? If yes, please describe the products and specify the Technology readiness levels (TRL 1-9).¹

The institute currently is not developing CD&E or M&S tools, nor has it done so in the past. It is applying such methods (or elements from it) where appropriate, respectively could apply it when necessary. However, the institute in the past was active in the development of the “Disruptive Technologies Assessment Game” (DTAG) within NATO-RTO-Task-Forces SAS-062 (Assessment of Possible Disruptive Technologies for Defence and Security) und SAS-082 (Disruptive Technologies Assessment Game, DTAG). The institute's role, however, was to contribute with foresight and technological expertise to this serious gaming approach, not to the technical development of the supporting IT-tool, which was done by HCSS. In terms of TRL assessment, this supporting IT-tool at that time has reached probably something like TRL 6 (prototype in operational environment), but has considerably evolved over time towards the “Disruptive Technology Experiment (DTEX)”, as developed and executed by NATO’s Innovation Hub, supported by full-scale M&S.

The institute, however, has further developed and applied a variant of the table-top exercise method e.g. in EU security research projects.

5. What experimentation methods have been used for testing and validating the technological concepts of your main products?

We involve the end-users (crisis management teams, firefighters, police, etc.) via interviews, focus groups, workshops, questionnaires.

6. Have gender aspects been considered in the development of your main products? Please, specify how. Do your products contribute to gender equality?

Yes, the recruitment process for workshops, interviews and also for table top exercises and full-scale exercises themselves include gender aspects. Admittedly, if we wish to include fire-fighters in the list of participants, and only male firefighters work for the respective organisation, there is not much we can do about it.

7. Does the Institute provide free access to some products for academic and research purposes?

Not applicable.

8. What are the most important lessons learned (positive and negative) from the participation of the Institute in EU security research and innovation projects (under FP7 and H2020)?

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/wp/2014_2015/annexes/h2020-wp1415-annex-g-trl_en.pdf

- Explain in detail the technical solutions we want to develop in the projects to the respective end-users before the start of the project itself
- Include in an iterative process the experience and needs of the end-users
- Have a clear idea of what should happen after the project (who will buy it? Is it affordable? Issues of standardisation? Legal aspects? User acceptability?)
- Communication is key – usually in the first year of the projects technical partners and end-users tend to live in parallel worlds.

Interview no.10 with a representative of ISA Intelligence & Science Applications

Date: 03/06/2021

1. Describe briefly the research and innovation products of your company which are most relevant for EU conflict prevention and peace-building.

- Our company does not develop specific products.
- We create methodologies, strategies, and implement them with our experts and technologies.
- Our company is technology agnostic to ensure the best satisfaction of our customers.

2. What could be the potential role of CBRNe & OSINT expertise in EU peacebuilding missions and operations?

- CBRNe are non-conventional threats and they potentially can have high impact on countries, including on developing countries where EU peacebuilding missions and operations take place.
- CBRNe threats are disruptive for the whole society.
- CBRNe should be part of peacebuilding activities along with the fight against conventional terrorism. In some unstable developing countries, there are critical infrastructures such as laboratories up to BSL4, high-risk chemical facilities, etc. that could be source of risks.
- CBRNe is very relevant for EU peacebuilding missions and operations.
- OSINT (Open source intelligence) is a means to achieve our objectives. In 99% capacity-building is actually not training but raising awareness due to the limited amount of time experts are deployed in the countries.
- There should be more emphasis on capacity-building which is a much broader concept than trainings and it includes normative capacity.
- And this is where OSINT should be integrated to support countries in centralizing key information such as regulations, legal texts, in addition to best practices.
- There is currently a lack of or no Knowledge Management System (KMS) in developing strategies which render impossible to capitalize on trainings, capacity-building activities at large.
- International actors are not adequately using knowledge management systems. For example, there are more than 20 projects on hazardous waste that are / were conducted in developing countries but there is a lack of synergies and information sharing. Cooperation agencies work in silos, competing with others instead of mutualizing efforts for the benefit of developing countries.

3. Does your company develop peace-tech (peace-related technologies)?

- Our company is technologically agnostic. We have our technological preferences and we can adapt our solutions according to the customers' needs be it industry or governments.
- Peace-tech has to be agnostic. The tools and technologies delivered by the international actors for the developing countries should be useful for those countries, even if a low-tech approach would better fit rather than promoting advanced solutions that are not matching needs and capabilities of the countries.

4. Is your company active on the European market for research and innovation products for EU conflict prevention and peace-building? How can a SME be competitive on the European market?

- There is a lack of coordination and synergies between research and innovation on one side, and capacity-building on the other.
- Until recently DG DEVCO and DG HOME barely talked to each other and there are no sufficient links between the EU research programmes (DG HOME) and the cooperation development programmes (including in the CBRNe area) (DG INTPA ex. DEVCO)
- There is a simple way to make SMEs more competitive just by reducing the eligibility criteria for SMEs leading or participating in research and innovation projects.
- Currently, newly established SMEs can act as partners (member of the consortium) but in reality they are most likely invited as subcontractors.
- The European Commission must realize that a high % of activities conducted in research and innovation is currently conducted by SMEs as a subcontractor in shadow, sometimes against the EU rules.
- By unlocking the regulations to allow SMEs in participating as partners or even coordinator would definitely boost EU competitiveness industry.

5. Does your company make use of tools for modelling and simulation (M&S), wargaming or gaming for peace?

- Yes, we make use of M&S tools although it is not our core business.
- For example, we make use of Aloha (hazard modelling programme) and CFD software.
- They are very useful specifically for visualisations.

6. Does your organization make use of tools for concept development and experimentation (CD&E)?

- We make use of CONOPS for all our projects

7. Has your organization been involved in international research and innovation projects in the area of modelling and simulation, wargaming, gaming for peace or concept development and experimentation (CD&E)? Please specify (name of project, funding source etc.).

- I would place our capacity building projects first (we have implemented such projects in 20 countries) and R&T projects second.

8. What experimentation methods have been used for testing and validating concepts in your company?

- We implement an iterative process in the company with the active involvement of end-users.
- From end-users' requirements to end-users' validation, we have tight connections with our customers and privilege workshop sessions to make incremental changes if needed.

9. Have gender aspects been considered in the development of the research and innovation products in your company? Do your products contribute to gender equality?

- In capacity-building projects gender balance is not an issue
- However, in R&T projects gender balance is still an issue (especially in areas such as software modelling).

10. What are the main strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats with regard to the research and innovation process in your company as a unique SME in Europe specialized in CBRNe & OSINT?

- As an SME we are agile and versatile.
- We have no restrictions, we are independent, and have many partners across the globe to satisfy our customers with bespoke solutions.

Interview no.11 with an official from the European External Action Service (EEAS)

Date: 04/06/2021

1. What are the main strengths and weaknesses of the EU conflict Early Warning System (EWS)?

We are measuring the strengths and weaknesses of the EU conflict Early Warning System (EWS) in an annual exercise. The main strength is that the EWS is based on a unique evidence-based tool, the GCRI. The GCRI is developed by the JRC and it is the scientific basis for classifying countries in terms of the risk of violent conflict. On this scientific basis we launch a qualitative assessment with stakeholders and carry out structural country assessments. Finally, the group exercise is carried out in a set of chosen country outside the EU that cannot be explicitly mentioned because of sensitivity reasons.

The main weakness is that the dynamical elements are not fully included in the model. Another weakness is the need to improve the link between early warning and early action.

2. Describe briefly how your unit contributes to implementing the EU's integrated approach. Which are the major shortcomings of the integrated approach from the perspective of a practitioner?

The integrated approach is implemented in the shared assessment phase (of the annual exercise) and the following discussions on potential actions. All the actors and stakeholders are put together and we focus on conflict sensitivity. Having said that, I partly agree that the conflict sensitive approach is not widely used and discussed.

3. Has your unit made use of the results from EU research and innovation projects in the area of EU conflict prevention? Please specify the name of the project/s and how they were helpful in your work.

No. We are collaborating mainly with the JRC. We are making use of the Science for peace portal. Also, we are exchanging best practices with other organizations such as the UN.

4. What are the main lessons learned from the development and implementation of the Global Conflict Risk Index (GCRI)? How does GCRI support the EU's external action and conflict prevention in practice?

One of the main lessons learned is that we must integrate the dynamic elements in the system. Another lesson learned is to make the conflict definition more precise. Many elements are not adequately taken into account in the model. The GCRI is the backbone of the Early Warning System and is very important for EU conflict prevention. We are also trying to promote the use of the GCRI in other areas such as conflict analysis, situational awareness. The buy-in from the political side is still complicated.

5. What is the added value of Artificial Intelligence (AI) approaches for the GCRI?

Don't have a clear answer for the moment. We are doing some experiments in this direction but so far, the results are disappointing. Artificial intelligence could support the GCRI especially in terms of exploiting the infinite quantity of available data.

6. How would you address critique that information and analyses on external conflicts and crises are easily available from the media, hence, the application of quantitative tools such as the GCRI seems pointless.

First, the GCRI is structuring data from open sources in a way which is not available in the media. Second, the JRC as an independent guardian of the system provides for data reliability. This is a guarantee of independence.

We also have contacts with other EU bodies which are doing conflict-related studies such as the EU Institute for Security Studies (EUISS).

7. Have gender aspects been taken into account in the development of the GCRI?

Not yet but this issue is getting ever more relevant. So, we've started a discussion and we are working on these aspects as well.

8. How could the GCRI model be optimized in the future to better represent the complexities of real-world conflicts? For example, how could the GCRI address complex realities, such as hybrid peace or hybrid conflict?

There is currently a review of the GCRI indicators going on. New elements and indicators may be added such as hybrid threats, disinformation, the pandemic, compound risks, the gender dimension and election-related violence. All of them are part of the current discussion. It should be taken into account that the datasets for the model include data for 25 years.

Interview no.12 with a representative of XVR Simulation

Date: 08/06/2021

1. Describe briefly state-of-the-art products of your company which are most relevant for EU conflict prevention and peace-building. Please, define the type of the product: service; software; hardware; platform; studies or other. Please, specify the TRL (Technology readiness levels) of the product in line with the EU definitions (TRL 1-9).²

All simulation tools developed by the company are based on a 3D games simulator, they represent a small 3D world up to a full region/country including the digital information (media) channels. It is neither a shooting simulator, nor a command and control (C2) simulator. In the XVR Simulation platform multiple players (students/participants) can be immersed in any type of incident/crisis scenario built and controlled by the instructor/operator. It is specifically designed to train and assess emergency response and rescue professionals. It is suitable for civil-military use but not for purely military tasks. Apart from training people, the simulation tool could be used for assessing the trained personnel, the procedures, the communication lines as well as assessing new tools. The simulation platform is relevant for EU peacebuilding, for example for assessing procedures or commanding incident situations in a humanitarian intervention or a refugee camp.

The different modules of the XVR Simulation platform have TRLs, as follows:

XVR On scene module – TRL 9

XVR Crisis media – TRL 9

XVR Resource Management TRL 7/8

XVR Expo – TRL 9

XVR After Action Review – TRL 8

2. Does your company develop peace-tech (peace-related technologies)? Please, specify?

Yes, we develop peace-tech for the police, fire and medical services. These peace-tech could be used, for example in humanitarian camp management and crisis response exercises (e.g. natural disaster, terrorist attack, et cetera).

3. Has your organization been active on the European market for ICT products for EU conflict prevention and peace-building? For example, are you selling products to EU institutions, EU peace-building missions or operations?

² https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/wp/2014_2015/annexes/h2020-wp1415-annex-g-trl_en.pdf

We do not sell products directly to EU institutions, but indirectly through national and regional institutions and academies we provide products for training and civil protection exercises to EU institutions such as DG ECHO and DG HOME.

4. Does your company develop tools for modelling and simulation (M&S), wargaming or gaming for peace? In your view could the XVR® Simulation Platform be used in scenarios for EU conflict prevention and peacebuilding?

Yes, the XVR Simulation platform is a tool for M&S and it is actively used as a virtual simulation world, a virtual reality incident scene. References to the Matrix movie are not ungrounded.

5. Does your company make use of concept development and experimentation (CD&E) in the research and development (R&D) process?

Yes, we make use of CD&E in the R&D process. Different end-users make use of different terms. The term CD&E lives mostly in the military field. The civilian 'blue light' services would rather use 'trial and error'. Some would say 'piloting' or 'proof of concept' (in the software business). But the principle is actually the same, a reiterative process of testing.

6. What are the major international research and innovation projects of your company which have relevance for the European Union's policy area of conflict prevention and peacebuilding?

The major project is the ongoing process within DG ECHO of reforming the civil protection training and exercises at the EU level.

7. What are the most important lessons learned for your company from the DRIVER+ project?

The main lesson learned was the use of the CD&E methodology (see, for example the DRIVER+ Methodological guide). Hammering a glossary makes sense.

On the other hand, it was an extremely big and slow project. The political decision was to focus on disaster response.

One of the spin-offs of the the DRIVER+ project is the STRATEGY project (coordinated by TNO).

8. What experimentation methods have been used for testing and validating the concept of the XVR® Simulation Platform?

It is a semi-unstructured process of design and iterations. The customers play a major role for validating the concept. Another structured assessment method is the so-called introspect model by

keeping track of incident commanders' assessments. Third, in the DRIVER+ project the XVR platform was assessed by large-scale exercises.

9. Have gender aspects been considered in the development of your main products? Please, specify how. Do your products contribute to gender equality?

Yes, 1) the amount of avatars is very diverse; and 2) the psychological aspects in gender terms should be taken into account.

10. What are the major strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats (SWOTs) with regard to the company's R&D?

Overall, the emergency services have lower budgets than the military and are more busy with operational tasks. So, the emergency services have pragmatic ways, which can be seen as a strength as it can fast-track innovation. On the other hand, the military have more time to train which is a strength for them.

The pragmatism is a weakness as well, as it can lead to unstructured assessments and experimentation, thereby making the results questionable.

Opportunity is the very short operation cycle at emergency services. This can lead to quick innovations and quick adjustments thereof.

Threat is the unstructured nature of the process sometimes caused by (over-)pragmatism. Lack of valid results can lead to budget cuts on innovative projects.

XVR Simulation is the world's leading developer of simulation technology within the emergency services field.

Interview no.13 with a representative of KEMEA

Date: 14/06/2021

1. Describe briefly state-of-the-art products of your organization which are most relevant for EU conflict prevention and peace-building. Please, define the type of the product: service; software; hardware; platform; studies or other. Please, specify the TRL (Technology readiness levels) of the product in line with the EU definitions (TRL 1-9).³

Our organization actually does not develop commercial products. We prepare studies, deliverables, technical specifications, pilots, demos and user requirements. But we do not develop commercial products.

2. Does your organization develop peace-tech (peace-related technologies)? Please, specify?

Again, we do not produce technologies.

3. Is your organization active on the European market for ICT products for EU conflict prevention and peace-building? For example, has your organization attempted to sell products to EU institutions, EU peace-building missions or operations?

We are active on the European research and innovation market but we do not sell ICT products to EU institutions, missions or operations.

4. Does your organization develop or use tools for modelling and simulation (M&S), wargaming or gaming for peace?

We do not develop such tools but we have made use of platforms developed by our technical partners in research projects.

5. Does your organization develop or use tools for concept development and experimentation (CD&E)? If yes, please describe the product and specify the TRL.

We are not familiar with tools for CD&E and we do not make use of such tools.

6. What are the major international research and innovation projects of your organization in the European Union's policy area of conflict prevention and peacebuilding?

³ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/wp/2014_2015/annexes/h2020-wp1415-annex-g-trl_en.pdf

We have several projects in the area of border management and border surveillance. The only project we have in the European Union's policy area of conflict prevention and peacebuilding is the CIVILnEXT project. The project was redefined, its scope was changed and we are still waiting for green light to continue with the project, including the procurement procedures.

7. What are the most important lessons learned from the CIVILnEXT project?

Its is still early to speak of lessons learned. The procurement procedures under the project have still not started.

8. Describe briefly the Operation Control Platform developed under the CIVILnEXT project. What experimentation methods have been used for testing and validating the operational concept?

We are only drafting the basic requirements and modules of the platform (such as Common operational picture, C2, etc.). The tenderers will present their solutions in the procurement procedure.

9. Have gender aspects been considered in the development of your main products? Please, specify how. Do your products contribute to gender equality?

Yes, these aspects have been considered in the procurement documents and the tenderers will have to address it.

10. What are the major strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats (SWOTs) with regard to the organization's research and development activities?

The main strength of our organization is its status, a private organization under public law which makes it more flexible and easy to adapt. We have a large pool of experts from the security sector (Police, Army, MoD and the Coast Guard). A major threat is the risk of not approval of submitted proposals.

Interview no.14 with a representative of Stam

Date: 16/06/2021

1. Describe briefly state-of-the-art products of your company which are relevant for EU conflict prevention and peace-building. Please, define the type of the product: service; software; hardware; platform or other.

We are an engineering company for R&D services and high-tech solutions. We do not provide products but services, including consultancy services. So far, we have not tackled conflict prevention and peacebuilding, however, we have done R&D in related areas: security of public spaces, security of critical infrastructures, transport security. we have done agent-based modelling and simulation of environments, events. We have simulated terrorist attacks. So, our know-how is applicable to EU conflict prevention and peacebuilding and, specifically in terms of modelling and simulation of procedures, missions and operations.

2. Does your company develop peace-tech (peace-related technologies)?

As mentioned, we do not produce technologies but our services are relevant for peace-tech.

3. Does your company participate actively on the European market for ICT products for EU conflict prevention and peace-building? For example, is your company selling products to the European External Action Service, European Defence Agency, EU peace-building missions or operations?

So far, we have not participated in tenders / calls for ICT products for EU conflict prevention and peace-building.

4. Are some of the products of your company which are developed for the European Space Agency also relevant for the EU's Common Security and Defence Policy?

The company was founded thanks to funding provided by the European Space Agency (ESA) Technology Transfer Programme to develop an innovative gearbox system. Since then the company has been successfully collaborating with the ESA in the development of special mechatronic devices (pure technology) for space missions. we are also involved in projects on Earth Observation under the Copernicus programme.

5. Does your company develop tools for modelling and simulation (M&S), wargaming or gaming for peace?

We do not develop tools for modelling and simulation but we make use of such tools. We use M&S tools to develop customized tools for specific customers.

6. Does your company develop tools for concept development and experimentation (CD&E)?

We do not develop tools for CD&E.

7. Has your company been involved in international research and innovation projects in the area of modelling and simulation, wargaming, gaming for peace or concept development and experimentation (CD&E)?

Yes, in the last 10 years the company has been involved in research and innovation projects for M&S, critical infrastructure protection and vulnerability assessment under FP7, H2020 and ISF-Police.

8. What experimentation methods have been used for testing and validating the technological concepts of your main products?

The end-users and stakeholders are actively involved in the process of testing and validating the technological concepts. These concepts are developed to meet the requirements defined.

We also had a project on AI techniques to assess to what extent our products are close to real life.

9. Have gender aspects been considered in the development of your main products? Please, specify how. Do your products contribute to gender equality?

Gender aspects have been considered and they have never been a problem in our company.

10. Does your company participate in major EU industrial exhibitions (e.g., Defence and Security Equipment International – DSEI and the International Forum for the Military and Civil Simulation, Training and Education Community – ITEC)?

So far, no.

11. How do you carry out the technology assessment and optimisation of your company's main products? What are the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats with regard to the company's R&D activities?

The inputs from the end-users are crucial.

We are a small engineering company, an SME.

The main strength is that we have all kinds of expertise, so we can engage in a wide range of projects. Another strength is that being small makes us flexible. On the other hand, we cannot do some large projects on our own.

We see plenty of opportunities, especially in terms of developing M&S tools.

The main threat comes from large companies which are doing M&S as their core business and they are very strong competitors.

Interview no.15 with a representative of the German Council on Foreign Relations

Date: 16/06/2021

1. Describe briefly in what ways does the German Council on Foreign Relations (DGAP) practically help for enhancing the European foreign and security policy?

DGAP practically helps for enhancing the European foreign and security policy through policy-oriented research, practice-oriented advice and awareness raising for policy-makers and practitioners. The research we conduct is practical; it is done in different formats. In some cases we conduct policy forums in closed format (under Chatham House rules) but we also have events that are open to the public and aim to contribute to a more informed foreign policy discourse in Germany. DGAP is a member-based organization and everyone can become a member.

2. What are the main research projects of the German Council on Foreign Relations in the area of EU conflict prevention, peacebuilding and civilian crisis management?

Our main research projects in this area are a project on the Strategic Compass, a project on Civilian Crisis Management, a project on conflict prevention and peacebuilding in the Sahel region and the Horn of Africa, a project on stabilization. Some of our projects are also related to other DGAP research programmes, e.g. on migration.

Our funding is diversified, coming from i.a. national (MFA, MoD) or international (EU) bodies and foundations.

3. Is military crisis management fully excluded from the research priorities of the German Council on Foreign Relations?

No, military crisis management is not at all excluded from the DGAP research priorities. We are working on military crisis management, armaments policy and other defence-related issues. But, indeed, the German policy focus is on civilian crisis management or at least the comprehensive approach.

4. What research methodologies and tools are employed in the DGAP research work on EU conflict prevention and peacebuilding?

Some of the main research methods employed are interviews, scenario workshops, informal chats. More recently, we have also done a Delphi study and quantitative analyses.

5. Are tools for modelling and simulation (M&S), wargaming or gaming for peace used in the DGAP research work? If yes, please specify the product/s.

No, such tools have not yet been used in the DGAP research work. The only exception being scenario workshops and a project on foreign policy and gaming

6. Is NATO's methodology for Concept development and experimentation (CD&E) employed in the research projects of the German Council on Foreign Relations?

No, the CD&E methodology is currently not employed in DGAP research projects.

7. Does the German Council on Foreign Relations have collaborations with the European academia and the research industry?

Yes, there are such collaborations but mostly on a case by case basis.

8. How are gender aspects addressed in DGAP research on European foreign and security policy issues?

We do not have a specific programme on gender but most of our research addresses gender aspects (for example, women in ISIS, etc.).

Interview no.16 with an official from DG Migration and Home Affairs

Date: 17/06/2021

1. Could we speak of a fully developed European Union (EU) security research policy? What is the role of the security research programme in EU policy-making?

Security research in the EU is relatively young. After a small-scale preparatory action security research in the EU actually started under FP7 in 2007. So, it is still a 'teenager' but it is constantly evolving and becoming something quite robust. We are continuously learning. Security research has evolved throughout the years. Initially, it was managed by DG Enterprise and Industry and was closely connected with the EU industrial policy. But afterwards, in H2020 security research management was transferred to DG HOME. Now security research is seen as a building block, a strategic enabler of the EU's security policy. Security research should contribute to making Europe a safer place. The proportion between the industrial dimension and the security policy dimension has changed. Security research is now mostly policy-driven.

Security research has been often under the spotlight. But even in its early years security research was not driven by industrial lobbying but mostly by the Member States and EU policy priorities.

2. What are the main policy documents and legal acts regulating the EU's security research policy?

The main legal act is the overall EU Framework programme (FP) for research and innovation. It is not precise to speak of security research programme as it is part of the overall FP.

There are many relevant policy documents, the most important being: the EU Security Union Strategy, the New Pact on Migration and Asylum, the EU Action Plan on Firearms Trafficking, the EU Action Plan to support the protection of public spaces, the EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change, the EU Border Management Strategy, the EU Maritime Security Strategy, the EU Civil Protection Regulation, the Directive on Security of network and information systems (the NIS directive), the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (at UN level), etc. Most of these policy documents explicitly refer to the development of technologies and innovations in their specific areas.

3. Which are the main EU institutions in charge of security research? Please, explain the role of DG Migration and Home Affairs in managing EU security research.

Under the new research and innovation programme Horizon Europe the so-called co-creation approach is implemented. At the highest level the European Parliament and the Council adopt the overall legal base for the FP, including for security research. Then, the Commission does the nitty-gritty. Under Horizon Europe the security research Work programme is drafted by all the competent DGs involved with 3 co-chairs (DG HOME, DG Connect and DG RTD). In practice, most of the DGs are on the table (DG ECHO, DG CLIMA, DG MARE, DG JUST, etc.). Other EU entities are also involved, for example EU agencies such as FRONTEX, EUROPOL, EU-LISA, etc. The EEAS is also involved in the

process; it has contributed with identifying requirements and topics for the external dimension of security research, especially in the beginning of H2020.

4. How are the topics (and their respective budgets) in the annual security research programme defined? What is the role of DG Migration and Home Affairs and other EU institutions? How do you manage and reconcile different institutional and national interests in this process?

It is a very complex and structured process. It takes 2 years to write the security research WP. Drafting the WP is a process of constant negotiation with all the actors. Usually, we start from the budget but this year the budget was not clear from the outset; it became clear at a very late stage.

The process of drafting is actually a game of ping-pong with 3 players – European Commission services (the DGs), other EU bodies (agencies) and the Member States (the Programme Committee with national representatives). We have basically two sets of inputs coming from the EU and the Member States. The task of our unit is to facilitate the process and act in a diplomatic way. It is important each party to take ownership of the final result (the work programme).

5. For many academics the EU's Common Security and Defence Policy (CSDP) and, more specifically EU conflict prevention and peacebuilding are not sufficiently addressed in the EU security research programmes? In this context, how could the European Commission's geopolitical ambitions for Europe as a global actor be achieved without adequate research funding in this crucial area?

The relevant actors have been fully involved in the WP drafting process. The EEAS can make an appreciation of what could be achieved by research projects. It is not the responsibility of my unit to define the topics for this policy area.

Security research is for civil applications only. Defence research is to be funded under the new defence research schemes.

6. Are there procedures for involving civil society organizations in the EU security research programme? Are independent experts involved in this process?

The drafting of the security research WP is responsibility of the Commission services and the Member States. No other actors are involved (neither the industry, nor civil society organizations - CSOs or experts). Having said that, it should be underlined that it is fundamental to involve CSOs in security research. The civil society perspective is very important. We invite CSOs to our workshops, they have been involved in advisory groups. In some topics under Horizon Europe the involvement of CSOs as partners is mandatory.

7. Has your unit made use of the results from EU research and innovation projects? If yes, please specify the projects and how they were helpful in your practical work.

My unit has not made use of the results as we do not have operational functions. In most cases technologies developed under research projects will be used by the Member States.

8. In your view how could cooperation between research and policy at the EU level be enhanced?

It is fundamental to get everyone on the same table. We have identified 5 main players in security research: policy-makers, end-users, researchers, the industry and civil society organizations. Very often these players speak different languages. Security research should be acknowledged as a building block in the capability development process at the EU level. This process starts from defining policy requirement and goes through operational requirements, identifying gaps and the final acquisition.

9. How are gender aspects taken into account in your unit in the process of drafting the security research programme?

Gender aspects are fully taken into account. Under Horizon Europe gender is one of the horizontal issues. Each proposal has to address gender aspects.

Interview no.17 with a representative of TNO

Date: 18/06/2021

1. Describe briefly the experience of TNO in Concept Development and Experimentation (CD&E).

Within TNO Defence, Safety and Security the CD&E approach has been widely used for a variety of defence research in the area of Command and Control (C2) for Land forces and the Navy, weapon systems, training programmes, doctrine (e.g., on littoral warfare). Outside of defence we have made use of CD&E for research in the area of national security; for example, in areas such as counter-terrorism, capability-based approaches, hybrid warfare (gaming and simulations).

2. To what extent and in which Work packages did the DRIVER+ project actually make use of the Concept development and experimentation (CD&E) methodology?

Within DRIVER+ the CD&E approach was the main basis for the trials and the project's methodology. We developed a test-bed and technical infrastructure for crisis management capability development under WP2. The methodological guide defines how to systematically test solutions. CD&E has also been applied in the technical infrastructure of the test-bed and the toolbox. The trials under WP4 have also been designed following the CD&E approach.

3. Does TNO currently make use of the CD&E methodology (for example, in follow-up projects to DRIVER+)?

TNO makes use of the CD&E methodology in a couple of EU-funded projects. For example, based upon the DRIVER+ methodology the STRATEGY project aims to improve the interoperability of systems, tools and operational procedures in the crisis management domain. The philosophy coming from the DRIVER+ project is the same. The methodology and the technical infrastructure are in use. There are also other EU-funded projects which make use of the CD&E approach based on DRIVER+ results – LINKS, ResponDrone, RESILOCK and TRESPASS.

4. Describe briefly the Advanced Concept Development & Experimentation Environment (TNO ACE). Has TNO ACE been used for experiments in the European Union's policy area of conflict prevention and peacebuilding so far?

An example of a TNO ACE model is a simulation model of the terrain and operational environment in Afghanistan (virtual battlefield) which is very realistic and useful for training Dutch Armed Forces. Within TNO ACE a whole variety of simulations have been developed.

Within TNO there is the Group Facility Room which facilitates brainstorming supported by IT systems. We also develop very realistic mockups of command rooms.

5. Does TNO develop CD&E tools, tools for modelling and simulation (M&S), wargaming or peace-tech (peace-related technologies)? If yes, please describe the products and specify the Technology readiness levels (TRL 1-9).⁴

We have a wide variety of pretty realistic M&S tools. We develop wargames with ICT support but also board-games (for example, on Improvised Explosive Devices).

We make use of commercial-off-the-shelf products.

6. What experimentation methods have been used for testing and validating the concepts of the main TNO research and innovation products in the area of defence, safety and security?

The main experimentation methods are: brainstorming; serious gaming; virtual experience by interactive human-in-the-loop simulations; and live experience through exercises.

7. Have gender aspects been considered in the process of creating innovations in TNO and in the CD&E process in particular?

Not explicitly, but in the last year in TNO there has been growing attention to gender aspects. In addition, in some cases gender is part of the research question.

8. Does TNO provide free access to some modules from the Advanced CD&E Environment for academic and research purposes?

Not really for free. The actual costs for using the facilities have to be covered.

9. In your view could some of the DRIVER+ research results be applied to the European Union's policy area of conflict prevention and peacebuilding? What are the experience and the ambitions of TNO in this research area?

Definitely, some of the DRIVER+ research results could be applied to the European Union's policy area of conflict prevention and peacebuilding. The DRIVER+ Trial Guidance Methodology coming from the disaster response area is also applicable to this EU policy area. The structure coming from the DRIVER+ portfolio of solutions could also be used in EU conflict prevention and peacebuilding. Very useful could also be the DRIVER+ online community for crisis management (Crisis Management Innovation Network Europe – CMINE). It would be easier and more cost-effective to make use of the DRIVER+ methodology and solutions in the EU policy area of conflict prevention and peacebuilding than to start from scratch. Most of our research is aligned with what our national stakeholders want to achieve in the area of external conflict prevention and peacebuilding, so we will support their efforts in this respect.

⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/wp/2014_2015/annexes/h2020-wp1415-annex-g-trl_en.pdf

Interview no.18 with a representative of The Hague Centre for Strategic Studies

Date: 23/06/2021

1. How do you strike the balance between quantitative and qualitative methods in HCSS research on defence & security issues? What is the added value of quantitative methods for HCSS research? Do you consider quantitative (data-driven) methods to be more 'precise', 'unbiased' and 'objective' compared with qualitative ones?

We always try to triangulate by using both quantitative and qualitative methods. First, we conceptualize, do extensive literature review and expert interviews, and operationalize. Then, we make use of qualitative methods and quantitative analysis (through the HCSS DataLab). This is often corroborated with case studies. Quantitative methods alone might not necessarily be more 'precise' and 'objective' but the use of quantitative methods, formalization and systematization has proven to be of value in many scientific domains, including the social sciences. Combining qualitative with quantitative methods allows for better comparability and replicability, greater efficiency, and *ceteris paribus*, higher predictive performance of the output.

2. Describe briefly the history of the HCSS DataLab? How has the initial idea evolved over the years?

The DataLab started out in 2007 to map risk areas in the world based on open-source data. GIS was added to develop a digital world map with countries at risk. The focus is on intra-state conflicts (civil wars). We conducted a comprehensive literature review of the academic qualitative and quantitative causes of conflict literature, in addition to reviewing a variety of composite indexes (e.g., the State Fragility Index) and explicitly predictive models (e.g, the PITF model). On that basis defined 50 drivers of vulnerability, described their relationship with political instability, and collected data which we uploaded in a GIS system. We then replicated and emulated various existing predictive econometric models which we further improved by adding other combinations of structural and automated event data. Our latest generation models employ machine learning to generate conflict predictions at the sub-national (district) level with a time horizon of 1-24 months. In the context of climate change, we have also developed specific climate-related conflict models within the global Water, Peace and Security (WPS) Consortium. We are currently working on a next generation causal conflict models which disentangle various conflict pathologies and the interaction effects between different drivers that lead to conflict in order to a) arrive at a better and more formal understanding of conflict onsets and b) with the 'black box' opened, facilitate the development of targeted policy interventions.

3. What software tools have been used for developing the HCSS DataLab's StratBase? Have you made use of tools for Concept development and experimentation (e.g., modelling & simulation tools) in the development of the HCSS DataLab's StratBase?

We do concept development and experimentation all the time. We make use of M&S tools, text mining tools, coding tools (Python, R), statistical software and data visualization tools.

4. How would you address critique that information and qualitative analyses on conflicts, political violence and security risks are easily available from the media, hence, the application of quantitative tools and datasets could be dismissed as a waste of resources.

We should not be constrained by a 19-th century outlook. For example, currently we have developed much more sophisticated weather models compared with 19-th century models. But also in the social sciences tremendous progress has been made in various fields precisely because of the use of more advanced and sophisticated tools and models.

5. Are you acquainted with the Global Conflict Risk Index (GCRI) which is defined as the evidence-based tool and backbone of the EU's Early Warning System?

The GCRI is a robust and relevant Index. Considerable work has been done by the people working on the GCRI over the years and its different iteration. Further improvements could focus on increasing the timeliness and the frequency with which it is updated, on increasing its predictive accuracy, and, in going beyond these high level structural factors, shedding light on the causal dynamics that lead to conflict.

6. Has the HCSS participated in research and innovation projects under the EU's research and innovation programmes (FP7, H2020) or the Preparatory Action on Defence Research (PADR)?

We have only participated in the predecessor programmes FP5, FP6 but not in H2020 because the success rates are low and the financial conditions not very attractive (one has to bring a lot of co-financing). We also feel that some of these programmes at times are focused more on facilitating knowledge dissemination (because of the size of the consortia and the transaction costs involved) and not so much on knowledge excellence.

7. In your view how could the HCSS DataLab's StratBase be used in the European Union's policy area of conflict prevention and peacebuilding? For example, could it be used in the planning of EU peacebuilding missions / operations?

Yes, the HCSS DataLab's StratBase definitely can be used in the European Union's policy area of conflict prevention and peacebuilding in three ways: our portfolio of predictive models; our causal conflict models (conflict pathologies); and our policy intervention models for conflict interventions.

8. Have gender aspects been taken into account in the development of the HCSS DataLab's StratBase?

Yes, gender aspects have been taken into account in the development of the HCSS DataLab's StratBase. We have included gender-related variables as input to the conflict analysis. We also assess the level of gender equality as a predictive factor.

9. How could the HCSS DataLab's StratBase be optimized in the future to better represent the complexities of real-world conflicts? For example, how could the HCSS DataLab's StratBase better address complex realities, such as hybrid peace or hybrid conflict?

The HCSS DataLab's StratBase can be optimized in the future to better represent the complexities of real-world conflicts in three ways. First, we need better data across a variety of domains. Second, we need to further develop new methods and models to better understand the world. Finally, every type of conflict is unique, so the solutions must be tailor-made. There is no one-size-fits-all solution.

Interview no.19 with a lawyer specialized in EU defence

Date: 01/10/2021

1. How would you address the critique in academic literature that EU defence is no more than a “social construct” or a “socio-technical imaginary”?

That would be an exaggeration. EU defence has substance, EU missions and operations are real. One should clearly define what is meant under EU defence. EU Defence Union does not exist, it is a project under construction, however, the CSDP is a real policy. The Treaty on EU (Art.42) refers to the progressive framing of a common Union defence policy. Of course, we must mention NATO which is engaged in the defence of Europe. It is a “catch 22” situation as some countries obstruct the development of EU defence as they believe it would endanger NATO at the price of subservience to the U.S. But doing so they prevent the construction of a European defence, which would be an alternative to NATO.

2. Given the unwillingness of Germany to support European defence integration how would you assess the willingness and capability of the French political class to establish France as the leader of EU defence?

France is well aware of the necessity of European defence and knows a lot about defence. Take for example nuclear deterrence which is really sophisticated. The increase of the cost of armaments should also be taken into account. There are three ways to ensure EU defence: 1) to do it alone; 2) to do it with the Americans and 3) to do it with Europeans. The 1-st option would be an enormous effort with such a high GDP for defence, making it socially unacceptable. The second option is actually not defence but actually means American protectorate. And American protection comes at a price. Therefore, the only desirable path is that of European defence.

3. Do you think that it would take a ‘Copernican revolution’ to move away from the current situation in EU defence planning? Three years later, do you see any prospects for a truly effective EU defence planning process?

There is one very fragile, very little ray of hope, a candle in the wind. And this is the ongoing Strategic Compass. I don’t really like the term “compass” as it only gives you the North but it does not show you the direction where we are heading to. It does not show you with which vessel, with which team. Is it collective defence, or crisis management or cyber defence? So, the Strategic Compass would not be enough. It must serve as a political guidance for the next European defence planning exercise.

4. In your view is it possible to regulate the entire EU defence planning process (CDM, CDP and CARD at the least) in a single legal act? What kind of act would be most appropriate given that the EU’s security and defence policy is predominantly intergovernmental in nature and in principle cannot be

“managed” like other EU socio-economic policy domains, by forward-looking regulations and directives?

This is almost impossible. As one EEAS officer has put it, this would mean “a bloodbath”. This is a question of power struggles between the EEAS, EUMS, EDA, the Commission and Member States. Actually no one wants to move. Once you move, you are dead. On a more optimistic note, the embryo CDM will probably survive. The CDP, however, which is not cyclical and the CARD will probably run out of steam.

5. How could EU defence as a public law phenomenon be related and harmonised with the EU’s peace-building and conflict prevention objectives set out in Art.21 (2) (c) Treaty on European Union?

Peace and defence are very much related. To give an example, when the EU was not able to enforce peace in Syria, then the refugee crisis that came later was inevitable. If the EU is not able to stop conflicts, then it must be prepared to pay the price. The very idea of the CSDP came in the 90s because the EU was not able to stop the genocide in former Yugoslavia.

The idea of strategic autonomy is present in the St. Malo declaration.

6. In your view could the new EU Defence-related initiatives (PESCO and EDF) deliver defence capabilities or will be no more than “a beauty pageant”?

As it was set up PESCO will lead nowhere. In the TEU PESCO was designed to be only for the willing and the able. PESCO is an integrative capability process aiming at the development of a capacity for autonomous action in order to solve international crisis. We are far from it. As every state is free to do whatever project with whoever it suits it, there is no added value to this mere cooperation in the framework of the Union. The likelihood it produces a real capacity is low. It is some sort of Mr Bean kind of planning.

On the other hand, the EDF is very promising but to be fully efficient proper EU defence planning is needed.

7. Are you familiar with the NATO methodology for Concept development and experimentation (CD&E) which plays an important supporting role in the NATO defence planning process (NDPP)? If yes, do you consider this methodology relevant for the EU defence planning process or just an additional burden?

No, I am not familiar with the methodology.

8. What is your view on the existing research on EU defence at the EU and Member States level? Is EU defence adequately informed by research? Could you propose measures for enhancing cooperation between research and policy in the area of EU defence and the wider Common Security and Defence Policy (CSDP)?

Until recently I held the opinion that the connection between policy and research on EU defence was not very good. Research in this area is over-complicated and gives no clear roadmap for policy-making. On the other hand, I doubt if the Member States would follow recommendations in the area of EU defence and the CSDP coming from research. It is a matter of sovereignty. But things might change, if the research is able to propose European leaders with clear analysis and ways ahead, how difficult they might be.

Interview no.20 with a representative of the EUNPACK project

Date: 07/10/2021

1. Looking back now what is the major contribution of the EUNPACK project in terms of research results? What is the project's research impact and how it can be measured?

Our impact has two parts. First, we had impact at the EU delegations level. We devoted considerable time to interviews. We did a lot of dissemination in the countries that we studied.

2. What is the policy impact from the EUNPACK project and how it can be measured? Do you see any "knowledge creep" of EUNPACK research results into EU policymaking?

Secondly, we had impact also at the "high" political level in the EEAS through our seminars. I would also not underestimate the informal impact we had by informal conversations but this is, of course, difficult to measure. I think we helped make the EU more aware of the limits of EU crisis management, that the local absorption capacity is low. We helped for a better overview of the projects. I think we helped in the rethinking some EU activities in the Balkans, specifically with regard to EULEX Kosovo and the troubled bridges of Mitrovica.

In terms of conflict sensitivity, I see small improvements. The EU has difficulties in mainstreaming conflict sensitivity; it is a matter of organisational culture.

3. What have been the major difficulties you faced when selling the project's research results to policymakers?

Many policymakers accepted our criticism, many acknowledged the need to reflect deeper in the problems. I think we had acceptance of our findings even when we talked about a foreign policy service which is not necessarily adequate.

At the delegation level they often had the feeling of being on the receiving end of politics which is developed in Brussels. At the headquarters level there is another frustration, the pressure on people to put policies in action, and the enormous reporting efforts.

4. Has the project contributed to establishing closer relations between your research team and EU policymakers / institutions?

Yes, it has brought us closer to EU institutions. But I have also mixed feelings. For example, when we organised some of our project events in Mali, we expected some EU institutions to be much more open.

5. Has the project contributed to the integration of your organisation in the European Research Area?

Yes, we have had previous research collaborations on EU matters but the project helped our core group of EU researchers further develop their capabilities.

6. In your view is there a clearly articulated EU research policy in the broad area of the EU's conflict prevention and peacebuilding, EU crisis management and the Common Security and Defence Policy (CSDP)? What measures could be taken to improve the EU's research policy in this specific area?

I am not certain there is a coherent research policy in this area. It needs critical research and there are a lot of things the EU could do. There is room for improvements. There is lack of continuity in the Horizon 2020 calls in this area.

7. Do you see politicisation as a problem in academic research on EU conflict prevention and crisis management? Do you think that objective, evidence-based and unbiased research is indeed possible in politically-charged areas such as EU conflict prevention and crisis management?

I don't see that much politicisation in this field. You can hear many diverse voices and many new ideas in this field. There can be politicisation around specific issues. There are other fields where politicisation is much stronger.

We had not experienced any pressure from the EU side when doing the research under the project.

8. Judging from your experience how would you characterize the interactions between the worlds of research and policymaking in the area of EU conflict prevention and crisis management? Could you propose measures for enhancing cooperation between research and policymaking in this area?

Well, first we must clarify how close are they supposed to be. I think there needs to be a distance between them. The world of research should do research and policymaking should not interfere.

The EU can improve the level of uptake of the research findings. There are no standard operating procedures in the EU in this respect. On the other hand, the researchers have to be better at preparing the research findings in a more user-friendly manner (of course, they can be critical). And the language must be as plain as possible.

Interview no.21 with a Professor in European Politics

Date: 12/10/2021

1. Judging from your experience what are the limitations of academic research in the area of the European Union's Common Security and Defence Policy (CSDP)? What is your view on the existing scholarship on CSDP? Is it feasible and indeed necessary CSDP to be based on sound theoretical foundations and informed by research evidence?

There have been various phases in the scholarship on CSDP. The first phase started from the 90-s and lasted until the late 2000-s. In this initial phase most people were broadly positive, enthusiastic and cheerleaders. The main theme was that CSDP should happen, that it is a good thing, research was cognitively positive. Gradually a mass of academic literature developed. From the late 2000-s, probably around 2009 the second phase began. Scholarship became narrower, and the focus was no longer on politico-strategic aspects. And this is a problem because the issues to be addressed are the big issues – the transatlantic relationship, the division of labour, the internal divisions in Europe.

In principle, yes, CSDP should be based on sound theoretical foundations and informed by research evidence.

2. In your view what are the horizons for future CSDP research? Could you outline a CSDP research agenda for the next 5-10 years? Which should be the main research strands?

To my mind the research agenda must focus on the big questions – the potential for reaching agreement on strategic issues, what will be the EU's stance to the clash between the US and China. The geostrategic chessboard is changing so fast. Without answers to the strategic questions research on CSDP will be in a vacuum. Of course, we also need objective evidence-based research on the new initiatives as the EDF.

3. Do you still maintain that theoretical approaches are not particularly helpful in understanding the empirical reality of CSDP? Do you consider Realism (or Neo-Realism) with its focus on nation-states to be a good fit for explaining the current state of play in the CSDP?

My take on theory derives from my methodological approach. I think it's more important to talk to policymakers and the military. Constructivist work can be useful, for example on issues related to strategic culture. When it comes to theory I am much more of a Realist. Realism (and Neo-Realism) is the only theoretical approach which really helps us understand the nature of the problem. If we do not address the fundamental questions of national interests and balance of power we are not getting anywhere. In fact, Neo-Realism could suggest that the EU will not be a global actor.

4. How could the current stagnation in the CSDP policy area be overcome in the foreseeable future? What is your view on the efforts to "re-launch" the CSDP and, specifically on the ongoing "Strategic

Compass” as the EU’s flagship policy initiative in the security and defence area? Do you see any prospects for strengthening the EU-NATO relationship and, possibly, for merging the CSDP into NATO?

The EDF is interesting, it has a lot of potential to rationalise. However, the sums involved are not terribly impressive. In fact, the funds are vastly inadequate. And we should note the absence of the UK.

PESCO is something of a standstill. The 47 PESCO projects do not address strategic enablers. Almost all Member States are involved. There is a lot of noise about PESCO but I don’t see breakthroughs.

Speaking about the Strategic Compass, we’ll have to see. The Compass is attempting to ask the right questions (threat analysis, political guidance, etc.) but we’ll have to see if the gulf between rhetoric and practice will be transcended. Or, it will be just another EU document.

For me the EU-NATO relationship is the most important question. CSDP has limitations and Europe should not be trying to be a security actor on its own. The EU can be a security actor only in tight cooperation with the US. So, the question is what is the optimal relationship, how could a “European pillar” in NATO be developed. It is a matter of agreement between the Europeans and the Americans. I think we should engage in a process of division of geostrategic labour. One option that I have maintained is a merge between the CSDP and NATO but presently I don’t see any prospects in this direction.

5. Throughout history knowledge has been actively used (and misused) to achieve political ends. Do you see politicisation as a problem in academic research on the CSDP? Do you think that objective, evidence-based and unbiased research is indeed possible in politically-charged areas such as the CSDP?

Well, this holds true to anything that has a political flavour in it. Nevertheless, I think that objective, evidence-based and unbiased research on CSDP is possible.

6. Are you familiar with the NATO methodology for Concept development and experimentation (CD&E) which plays an important supporting role in the NATO defence planning process (NDPP)? If yes, do you consider this methodology relevant for the CSDP and EU defence planning, in particular?

No, I am not familiar with the methodology.

7. In your view could we think of research and policymaking in the area of the CSDP as separate domains? Judging from your experience what are the interactions between the two? Could you propose measures for enhancing cooperation between research and policymaking in the area of the CSDP?

Indeed, the vast majority are stuck in their bunkers. In some cases, the think tanks are attempting to act as intermediaries. There is no magic wand to solve the issue.

Interview no.22 with a representative of the IECEU project

Date: 12/10/2021

1. Looking back now what is the research impact from the IECEU project?

Our researchers were part of the discussion on EU conflict prevention and peacebuilding. I think we had the strongest impact on the structures of the EEAS. We supported the establishment of the Conflict Prevention and Mediation Support Unit within the EEAS.

Also, very important were our field studies, for example the study on Afghanistan – gathering data with our local counterparts and hearing different views.

2. What is the policy impact from the IECEU project? Do you see any “knowledge creep” of IECEU research results into EU policymaking?

Our main contribution is in the understanding of capabilities, the developed framework of capabilities. This framework which was developed for conflict analysis has also been used in other fields. During the corona crisis the framework has been used in support of capability development to counter the risk from COVID-19.

3. What have been the major difficulties you faced when selling the project’s research results to policymakers?

The language of researchers and policymakers is different, so we needed to make sure that we speak the same language.

4. Has the project contributed to establishing closer relations between your research team and EU policymakers / institutions?

Yes, definitely. Actually, the project has strengthened partnerships existing before the project’s start. The funding instrument was new, we had joint activities (conferences, seminars). And our partnership has continued after the project’s end.

5. Has the project contributed to the integration of your organisation in the European Research Area?

It prepared the basis for the security studies at the university which coordinated the project. It has helped for the development of training courses. And they had also other projects in this area afterwards.

6. Has the project enhanced your research career and the career of other team members?

Definitely, yes.

7. In your view is there a clearly articulated EU research policy in the broad area of the EU's conflict prevention and peacebuilding, and the Common Security and Defence Policy (CSDP)? What measures could be taken to improve the EU's research policy in this specific area?

No, I don't think so. There is only a programme at the European Security and Defence College but this is not sufficient.

For us it was very challenging to publish research from the project. Journals are not keen to publish empirical research. They are not keen on publishing articles on conflict prevention and peacebuilding from a EU perspective. And it is difficult to define where this research belongs to – does it belong to International Relations, Political Science, Training and education or some other area?

8. Judging from your experience how would you characterize the interactions between the worlds of research and policy in the area of EU conflict prevention and peacebuilding? Could you propose measures for enhancing cooperation between research and policy in this area?

It is important to get all the actors together, in the same room for discussions. I think we achieved that in our project events.

Interview no.23 with the Editor-in-chief of a peer-reviewed journal

Date: 14/10/2021

1. How would you characterize the state of play in the academic publishing market in Europe? What are the major problems of a peer-reviewed journal in the area of international security which is based in Central Europe?

The overall business is dominated by big publishing houses with history. All journals are striving to improve their positions but it's difficult to climb up the ladder. The top journals receive loads of high-quality submissions which is not the case with lower ranking journals. We are trying to improve our position, to promote ourselves but it is difficult. Lower ranked journals are constrained by the structural conditions.

2. What are the main principles guiding your journal's editorial policy? More specifically, how do you ensure fairness and quality in the peer-review process?

In terms of reviewers' selection, we try to have both high-profile reviewers and early career scholars. Of course, the field of expertise is very important. We disregard super-brief reviews. As a pro-active editor I sometimes have to mediate between the reviewers when there is disagreement between them. So, in a way it is a process of triangulation of opinions.

3. Many Central and Eastern European scholars face difficulties in publishing in established international peer-reviewed journals which, as a rule, are based in Western Europe and edited by Western European academics (or in the U.S.). Do you think there is unequal treatment or discrimination against Central and Eastern European scholars by some international peer-reviewed journals?

No, I don't think there is unequal treatment. My papers have also been rejected and I think the procedure was fair. From my experience I can say that I sometimes feel more positively inclined to a submission if it comes from a country like Germany, for example.

4. What is your view on the current push in the academia to increase the policy impact of research? How could the policy impact of research articles be increased in practice?

My overall perspective is that the connection between policy and research exists but it is not always a direct connection. I am inclined to academic independence.

5. Throughout history knowledge has been actively used (and misused) to achieve political ends. Do you see politicisation as a problem in academic research in the area of international relations (IR) and

security? Do you think that objective, evidence-based and unbiased research is indeed possible in politically-charged areas such as IR and international security?

First, one must define what objectivity actually is. I don't think true objectivity is possible. Think about AI, even technologies have certain assumptions. It is difficult for the social sciences to be objective; social science research is a deliberative process. It requires a certain degree of autonomy of the academic sphere. Overall, I think that evidence-based science is needed.

6. What strategies could be undertaken by an academic journal to find an appropriate research niche, to sharpen the journal's focus and eventually increase its impact factor?

For example, journals can publish special issues on specific topics in order to advance the IF. Another option is to award some papers. All this requires bigger budgets and high reputation.

7. What measures could be taken by an academic journal to attract more high-quality articles in specific 'prestigious' research areas (e.g., European security and defence)?

It is questionable which research areas can be considered prestigious.

The Editorial Board is a very important body which has a role to play in attracting more high-quality submissions and promoting the journal. It is very important the journal to be added to new databases.

Of course, there is no miracle solution.

8. What is your view on the relationship between research and policymaking in the area of international security? How could cooperation between the two domains be enhanced? What is the role of peer-reviewed journals in this respect?

I would argue that there is an incremental interaction between these two fields.

Not all journals are interested in policy outreach.

Interview no.24 with a former member of NATO Allied Command Transformation

Date: 03/11/2021

1. What are the main strengths of the NATO CD&E method?

A few strengths: officially approved, 'known', there is a course, flexible in its application, stage-gate based. CD&E is approved by the Military Committee.

2. Could you give examples of some of the most successful NATO CD&E projects?

A very hard question. Concepts developed within NATO and accepted by NATO are not than many, probably between 20-25 overall.

Sometimes NATO concepts are copy-paste from nations.

One of the problems is the turnover of personnel. Some of the concepts are very high-level, telling everything and nothing.

3. What are the main weaknesses of the NATO CD&E method? Do you see a tension between CD&E as a policy process and CD&E as a scientific methodology?

The consensus rule as part of the decision process, the level of approval, the non-failure culture, the administrative burden. It is a policy process which means it must be consensual, all member states must agree on a concept. So, the process cannot be purely scientific.

In my view nations are more successful in CD&E than NATO.

4. To what extent does NATO make use of CD&E in the development of strategic-level (capstone) concepts? To your knowledge has NATO's Strategic Foresight Analysis (2017) been informed by CD&E?

To my knowledge, the two recent concepts did not follow the CD&E method as such.

CD&E should be informed by SFA, the other way is rather exceptional. CD&E is not directly feeding the SFA.

5. What is the relation of CD&E with Research and Development (R&D) and Science & Technology in NATO? Can CD&E be considered to be part of the research domain?

There could be a cyclic influence between those domains. R&D or/and S&T can inform CD&E while CD&E can guide R&D or/and S&T. There is interaction. Concepts are partly facts and partly a matter of belief.

If by research domain a scientific study domain is ment: yes, although it may be too limited unless it is expended with supporting sub-domains like analysis, M&S...

6. Judging from your experience how would you characterize the interactions between the research and policy domains in the area of defence? Could you propose measures for enhancing cooperation (or even integration) between research and policy in defence?

Research should inform policy based on facts. There must be freedom to think out of the policy box. Consensus based concepts have certain limitations.

7. What are your observations on the CD&E process in the European Union?

CD&E in the EU is more like doctrine development or current concepts, and less about innovating how things are done. In the EU concepts are completely different, they resemble AJP (Allied Joint Publications) which simply describe an existing system. There are no experiments in the EU.

8. Do you see any prospects for cooperation between the EU and NATO in the area of CD&E? In your view could CD&E be a potentially common area of interest and cooperation in the strategic partnership between the EU and NATO?

In a certain way it is already via the common members. A cooperations between the two organization would be possible, if the EU becomes interested in the topic. The EU could bring more civilian means to the table. It would be a great opportunity for the EU to demonstrate a willingness to cooperate with NATO without duplication.

Interview no.25 with a representative of the PeaceTraining.eu project

Date: 17/11/2021

1. Looking back now what is the main policy impact from the Peacetraing.eu project?

The project really made a difference. We've created new peace training curricula, including an original curriculum creator. We've also developed the PeaceTraining.eu platform which combines many elements, such as the handbook and different tools. The platform is still active after the project's end. The platform has about 10 000 visits per year which is a lot for a closed project. Open job positions are posted. We did a lot of work to raise awareness and reach out to policymakers. Direct contact was difficult, especially with high-level policymakers. So, it is difficult to measure the direct impact on policymakers but we were able to involve some policymakers at the project's final event. One of the project's achievements was that we helped many peace training organisations to be recognised as such, to show to the world what they are doing.

A positive development in terms of enhancing impact is the research results platform which has been recently launched by the EC.

2. What have been the major difficulties you faced when selling the project's research results to policymakers and end-users?

It was easier selling the project results to end-users as we had partners that are well-connected with end-users. More complicated was selling the project results to high-level policymakers. One of our achievements in this respect was an informal meeting with the Committee for Civilian Aspects of Crisis Management (CivCom) which was held in 2018 in Vienna. We were able then to present some of the project results and the PeaceTraining platform to policymakers. This is important because, in the end, we are making applied research. Very often for research projects it is very complicated to get to policymakers. I think there is a room for improvement in this respect regarding EU-funded security research projects.

3. Has the project contributed to establishing closer relations between your organisation and EU policymakers / institutions?

We had several connections and tried to involve EU institutions as much as possible. The EEAS was involved in the project's final conference. Very often this depends on individual persons.

4. Has the project contributed to the integration of your organisation in the European Research Area?

For sure. The project's topic was a fairly new one for us. It helped foster our position as a research and advisory organisation. We were able to successfully complete the project. There have not been many EU-funded calls in this area and in my view, there is a lot of capacity to be built.

5. Has the project enhanced your research / project management career and the career of other team members?

For me personally, yes. I had a coordinating role and the project played a capacity-building role for me and my colleagues. We got very good learning experience which was later used in follow-up projects such as SciShops. Of course, we also used PeaceTraining for advertising our company.

6. In your view is there a clearly articulated EU security research policy? What measures could be taken to improve the EU's research policy in this specific area?

In the security domain there are very different perspectives in the EU. Take Austria's neutrality for an example. So, it is difficult to articulate a security research policy at the EU level in a clear way. In my view the 'big' security topics, such as cybersecurity or organised crime are clearer. It gets more complicated when you get into the details and in some of the 'smaller' topics.

7. Judging from your experience how would you characterize the interactions between the worlds of research and policy in the security domain?

The interaction is complicated. It is really hard to establish direct contact with policymakers.

Beyond that, the EC could facilitate the uptake of projects' results, especially when we talk in terms of achieving the Single European Market and policies in support of SMEs. The EC can help increase the impact from research projects, especially for topics which are not very market-oriented. In the security domain there are topics for which there is no huge market opportunities. An interesting option in this respect would be the potential use of venture capital by the EC.